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DEVELOPING A GENDER SENSITIVITY INDEX FOR EXECUTIVE ORDER 70: MAINSTREAMING GENDER SENSITIVITY IN THE NATIONAL TASK FORCE TO END LOCAL COMMUNIST ARMED CONFLICT

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ABSTRACT

The development of a Gender Sensitivity Index (GSI) for mainstreaming gender sensitivity in the NTF-ELCAC under Executive Order 70 employed a whole-of-nation approach to address insurgency and promote social development, yet its sustainability hinged on integrating gendered roles, responsibilities, and decision-making into its framework, which enhanced women's active participation in peace-building and local development by addressing their unique needs and priorities. The study proposed a Gender Sensitivity Model to foster inclusion and improve community well-being, economic growth, and poverty reduction. Utilizing quantitative methods, the study identified key dimensions of gender sensitivity in the Davao Region and established a reliable GSI that guided future policy and program development within the Gender Development Framework of E.O. 70. The research emphasized the importance of embedding gender-responsive strategies, such as Collaborative Equity & Inclusivity, Shared Authority & Harmonized Security, Vigilance, Aid & Empowerment, and Integrated Response & Action, to improve gender equity, reduce GBV, and ensure sustainable, community-driven peace. Additionally, the study advocated for gender-sensitive monitoring and evaluation systems to enhance accountability and continuous improvement, while suggesting that future research incorporate gender-disaggregated data and intersectional analysis to refine policies and foster inclusive peace and security.

KEYWORDS: Gender Mainstreaming, Peacebuilding, Women's Participation, Capacity-Building, Empowerment Initiatives.

The study employed a whole-of-nation approach to address insurgency and promote social development, hinged on integrating gendered roles, responsibilities, and decision-making into its framework, which enhanced women's active participation in peace-building and local development.

The study proposed a Gender Sensitivity Model to foster inclusion and improve community well-being, economic growth, and poverty reduction. Utilizing quantitative methods, the study identified key dimensions of gender sensitivity in the Davao Region and established a reliable GSI that guided future policy and program development within the Gender Development Framework of E.O. 70. The research emphasized the importance of embedding gender-responsive strategies, such as Collaborative Equity & Inclusivity, Shared Authority & Harmonized Security, Vigilance, Aid & Empowerment, and Integrated Response & Action, to improve gender equity, reduce GBV, and ensure sustainable, community-driven peace.

1. INTRODUCTION

Gender sensitivity is vital in peacebuilding, facilitative women's meaningful participation addressing distinct needs. In the field of public safety, this approach fosters inclusivity and strengthens communities through fundamental causes of gender-based violence and ensuring that policies are attuned to gender differences which resulted in more effective and equitable solutions. In development studies, gender mainstreaming includes gender perspectives which benefits all genders. In fact, notable successes include Liberia's Women in Libera Mass Action for Peace, which led to a ceasefire and elected first female president. In Columbia, a woman secures gender equality in 2016 FARC peace agreement (22). Further, Sierra Leone's gender sensitive post-conflict policies and in Northern Ireland's women's role in enhancing Good Friday Agreements Inclusivity (25) which demonstrated that gender perspectives in peacebuilding leads to a sustainable solution.

In the Philippines, the gender perspectives are integrated into peacebuilding through the National Action Plan on Women, Peace, and Security 2023-2033 including the Barangay Development Program under the Executive Order No. 70, it is also aligned with UN Security Council Resolution 1325 advocacy women's roles in conflict resolution.

While Executive Order 70 promotes a Whole-of-Nation Approach to peace and development, the gender sensitivity perspective remains challenging. In fact, the Philippine Commission on Women is advocating for better integration of gender

perspective in decision-making. Added hereto, the Davao Region via localized peace dialogues and various community development programs achieved an insurgency-free status in 2023. Adversely, still the insurgent groups still trying the regain influence via spreading misinformation. With the help of gender-sensitive policies in E.O 70, ensuring the meaningful inclusion of women and marginalized group.

With these emerging challenges, the study aims to develop a gender sensitivity framework in the context of Executive Order 70 in the Davao Region. Particularly, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the dimensions of Gender Sensitivity in the context of E.O 70 in Davao Region?
2. What Gender Sensitivity Model in the context of E.O 70 could be developed?
3. What is the Gender Sensitivity Index of E.O 70: NTF-ELCAC in Davao Region?

2. METHODOLOGY

In this study, we choose to utilize quantitative research using the following statistical methods:

2.1. Overview Of the Multi Statistical Methods

This was used to determine the observable latent variables and explore possible outcomes of Executive Order 70; it is applied to explore the possible outcomes of Executive and its underlying implications for the initiated programs (11). Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), incorporating Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) followed by Relative Importance Index (RII) to provide a robust insight. To ensure cultural and contextual relevance in the settings of Davao Region, the questionnaire consists of sociodemographic profile such as age, gender, marital status, including geographical location. Using the Multistage Random Sampling, 385 respondents were collected from various provinces in Davao Region and from Davao City comprising of 385 samples. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) to determine the observable latent variables and explore possible outcomes of Executive Order 70, it is applied to explore the possible outcomes of Executive and its underlying implications for the initiated programs (11). Followed by Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to determine how effectively measured variables described for the total components (35). Ranking the factors based on their perceived importance, Relative Importance Index (RII) was used to determine the relative weight of various aspects based on responses gathered through surveys.

Table 1: Sampling Distribution Table.

Davao Region	Province Population	FORMULA Province= Province Population/Total Population of Region x Total Sample Size	Allocation of Respondents
Davao City	1,776,949	$\frac{1,776,949}{7,020,485} \times 385$	99
Davao de Oro	767,547	$\frac{1,776,949}{7,020,485} \times 385$	42
Davao del Norte	1,125,057	$\frac{1,776,949}{7,020,485} \times 385$	61
Davao del Sur	680,481	$\frac{1,776,949}{7,020,485} \times 385$	37
Davao Occidental	317,159	$\frac{1,776,949}{7,020,485} \times 385$	17
Davao Oriental	576,343	$\frac{1,776,949}{7,020,485} \times 385$	32
Total Regional Population	7,020,485		385 (Sample Size)

The following presents the Results and Discussions of the findings of the study.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Dimensions Of the Gender Sensitivity in the Context Of E.O 70 In Davao Region

Barlett's Test of Sphericity. Bartlett's Test of

Sphericity. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, which calculates the statistical likelihood that the correlation matrix contains significant correlations among some of its components, was a crucial step in determining the correlation matrix's overall significance. The significance of the data, $\chi^2 = 9348$ ($p < 0.001$), suggests that they are appropriate for factor analysis.

Table 2: Presented The Barlett's Test of Sphericity.

χ^2	df	P
9348	300	<.001

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin. The KMO measure of sampling adequacy assesses data suitability for factor analysis were yielding an overall value of 0.954, classified as "marvelous". Further, the individual KMO values ranges from 0.925 to 0.973, all

exceeding 0.90 which also indicates high adequacy of contributing to the factor structure. With these following results, the high KMO scores confirm the data set's suitability for factor analysis.

Table 3: Presented The Kaiser-Meyer Olkin

Overall	MSA
Overall	0.954
Item 1	0.963
Item 2	0.961
Item 3	0.965
Item 4	0.962
Item 5	0.964
Item 6	0.948
Item 7	0.969
Item 8	0.968
Item 9	0.935
Item 10	0.961
Item 11	0.931
Item 12	0.953
Item 13	0.95
Item 14	0.936
Item 15	0.965
Item 16	0.959
Item 17	0.952
Item 18	0.946
Item 19	0.945
Item 20	0.96
Item 21	0.953
Item 22	0.973
Item 23	0.931
Item 24	0.925
Item 25	0.967

Factor Loading. The factor loadings show how each item related to each other factors derived from principal axis factoring with varimax rotation. Factor loadings above 0.40 were considered meaningful. Factor 1 has a strong loadings from items S9 (0.850), S11 (0.817), and S14 (0.773) indicating a shared construct. For the factor 2, defined under the items S1 (0.682), S2 (0.677) and S3 (0.665). Added hereto, factor 3 I dominated by S24 (0.759), S23 (0.703), and S25 (0.623), as Factor 4 is defined by S19 (0.665), and S20 (0.857).

Some items display cross-loadings, such as S12 (loading 0.644 on Factor 1 and 0.462 on Factor 2) and S7 (loading 0.584 on Factor 2 and 0.441 on Factor 3), which may indicate overlapping constructs or shared variance between factors. Regarding uniqueness, items with low values, such as S9 (0.223) and S11 (0.221), have their variance largely explained by the

factors, while items with higher uniqueness, such as S8 (0.439) and S22 (0.536), retain a greater proportion of unexplained variance.

The varimax rotation, which aims to maximize the variance explained by each factor, has helped clarify the factor structure by concentrating high loadings on specific factors and minimizing cross-loadings. The results suggest a well-defined four-factor solution, with distinct groupings of items under each factor. These findings indicate that the items are generally well-represented by the model, although items with cross-loadings or higher uniqueness may warrant closer examination to ensure their alignment with the identified 30 constructs. This factor solution provides a strong basis for interpreting and naming the factors, aligning with best practices in exploratory factor analysis (10).

Table 4: Presented The Factor Loadings.

	1	2	3	4	Uniqueness
S9	0.850				0.223
S11	0.817				0.221
S14	0.773				0.264
S10	0.710				0.308
S13	0.699				0.274
S12	0.644		0.462		0.256
S4	0.579	0.449			0.37
S16	0.570				0.407
S6	0.558	0.483			0.384
S18	0.536				0.35
S1		0.682			0.294
S2		0.677			0.336
S3	0.440	0.665			0.286
S5		0.616			0.314
S7		0.584		0.441	0.325
S8		0.459			0.439
S24			0.759		0.243
S23			0.703		0.265
S25			0.693		0.289
S21	0.468		0.515		0.408
S19				0.694	0.237
S17				0.665	0.188
S20			0.475	0.587	0.274
S15		0.447		0.578	0.271
S22		0.404	0.506	0.536	0.253

Note: 'Principal axis factoring' extraction method was used in combination with a 'varimax' rotation

Reliability Test of Factors. The Cronbach's Alpha values for each of the four factors suggest excellent internal consistency and reliability. Factor 1, "Collaborative Equity and Inclusivity" with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.946, demonstrates very high internal consistency, indicating that the items within this factor reliably measure the same construct. This is an excellent result, although it may be worth checking for potential redundancy among items, as very high 31 values can sometimes indicate that items are too similar.

Factor 2, "Shared Authority and Harmonized Security," with an Alpha of 0.913, also shows

excellent internal consistency, suggesting that the items are consistently measuring shared authority in peace and harmonized voices in security. This factor is reliable, and minor refinements could be considered, though the overall result is strong. Factor 3, "Vigilance, Aid and Empowerment," has a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.893, reflecting good internal consistency. While this is still a reliable factor, there may be room for improvement if any items show weak correlations with the total score. Finally, Factor 4, "Integrated Response and Action," with an Alpha of 0.933, demonstrates excellent internal consistency. Like the other factors, this result suggests that the

items in this factor are highly reliable, though redundancy could be explored to further streamline the scale.

Overall, all four factors show strong reliability,

with Cronbach's Alpha values well above the acceptable threshold of 0.7, making them suitable for use in further analysis.

Table 5: Presented The Reliability Scale Statistics.

Factor	Dimensions	Cronbach Alpha
1	Collaborative Equity and Inclusivity	0.946
2	Shared Authority and Harmonized Security	0.913
3	Vigilance, Aid, and Empowerment	0.893
4	Integrated Response and Action	0.933

And finally, the results of the above processes are presented as it would mean that in theory and mathematically, the framework of the gender sensitivity in the context of E.O. 70 in Davao Region consists of dimensions such as:

Dimension 1 - Collaborative Equity and Inclusivity, supported by the study published in the International Organization of Scientific Research: Journal of Humanities and Social Science (2024) on gender-sensitive approaches to 32 women's involvement in constitution-making and peacebuilding emphasizes the vital role women have in promoting inclusive governance and lasting peace. Additionally, cited by (33) on gender-sensitive policies in Bangladesh highlights the country's commitment to enhancing women's empowerment and promoting gender equality through various initiatives.

Dimension 2- Shared Authority and Harmonized Security, according to the article "Beyond Gender Parity: Is Gender-Responsive Leadership in UN Peacekeeping the Missing Piece?" this was highlighted by the importance of women's leadership in peacekeeping operations (15). It argues that having gender-responsive leadership, especially at senior management levels, is vital for changing peacekeeping cultures and enhancing mission effectiveness. Furthermore, In the Philippines, the study *Bangsamoro: Women's Leadership in Peacebuilding by the Mindanao Peoples Caucus: The vital role women play in local peacebuilding, especially during the transition to the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM)* (39). It points out that although women are often sidelined in formal peace processes, they are crucial for fostering sustainable peace in conflict-affected regions like Mindanao. Their leadership is particularly significant in tackling the underlying causes of conflict, including economic inequality, human rights violations, and social exclusion.

Dimension 3 - Vigilance, Aid and Empowerment, as highlighted in the (39) report, "Financing for Gender Equality: Key Findings and Actions,"

highlights the vital importance of gender-sensitive budgeting for promoting women's economic empowerment and participation. The study 33 points out that women's needs are frequently underfunded in post-conflict situations, which hinders their engagement in peacebuilding initiatives. In the Philippines, the study "Women, Peace, and Security: Insights from the Philippines, (2021) highlights the necessity of incorporating gender-sensitive strategies into peacebuilding efforts, especially in conflict-affected areas like Mindanao. It stresses the crucial role women play in peacebuilding and the importance of including them in governance and resource management, which are often hindered by systemic obstacles.

Dimension 4 - Integrated Response and Action, according to the study of Gender-Based Violence in Conflict Settings: Understanding and Addressing the Impact: World Bank Report (2023), it is crucial to understand how GBV worsens in conflict situations and its wider effects on peace and security. It highlights that GBV, including sexual violence, is not merely a consequence of conflict but often a strategic tool used to destabilize communities, exert control over populations, and maintain systemic inequality. By examining the links between GBV, poverty, displacement, and weak governance, the study reveals the deep and lasting socio-economic and psychological impacts on survivors and their communities.

The Gender Sensitivity Model. The Gender Sensitivity Model in the Context of Executive Order 70 Model Fit Indices. To test the measurement model, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was carried out using JASP. The model fit measures (CMIN/df, GFI, CFI, TLI, SRMR, and RMSEA) used to evaluate the model's overall goodness of fit within the range of their common acceptability levels (38) The four-factor model [factor 1- Collaborative Equity & Inclusivity, factor 2 - Shared Authority & Harmonized Security, factor 3 - Vigilance, Aid & Empowerment, and factor 4 - Integrated Response & Action yielded the following (Fit Indices) for the

data: GFI= 0.997, 36 CFI = 0.971, TLI = 0.966, NFI = 0.968, SRMR = 0.042, IFI = 0.973, and RMSEA =0.119.

The significant chi-square statistic for the factor model ($X^2 = 545.995$, $df = 84$, $p < .001$) demonstrates that the model significantly improves upon the baseline model. While the p-value indicates that the model is not a perfect fit, the substantial reduction in

chi-square confirms that the factor model provides an appropriate and meaningful representation of the relationships among the variables. This supports the use of the factor model to explain the latent structure of gender sensitivity dimensions in the context of EO 70.

Table 6: Presented The Goodness of Fit.

Model	NFI	IFI	RFI	TLI	CFI	RMSEA	CMIN/DF
Default	0.968	.980		.966	.950	0.119	6.50
Saturated	1.000	1.000			1.000		
Independence	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.339	35.443

Path Diagram. The conceptual framework shown in the figure illustrates the interconnectedness of four factors: Collaborative Equity & Inclusivity (F1), Shared Authority & Harmonized Security (F2), Vigilance, Aid & Empowerment (F3), and Integrated Response & Action (F4). Each factor is intricately linked, reflecting a multi-dimensional perspective on gender sensitivity within the context of EO 70 in the Davao Region. The interplay of these factors can be contextualized and rationalized through the application of Social Capital Theory, Intersectionality Theory, Empowerment Theory, Feminist Institutionalism, Transformational Leadership Theory, and Systems Theory.

Collaborative Equity & Inclusivity (F1) is central to fostering relationships among stakeholders, as emphasized by Social Capital Theory (28). This factor underscores the necessity of building trust, mutual understanding, and equitable participation among diverse groups. Intersectionality Theory (7) further enriches this perspective by accounting for how 40 overlapping identities such as gender, ethnicity, and socio-economic status shape the experiences of collaboration. In the context of EO 70, which focuses on ending local armed conflicts, inclusivity ensures that marginalized voices, particularly women, are acknowledged and integrated into decision-making processes.

Shared Authority & Harmonized Security (F2) aligns with Transformational Leadership Theory (5), which emphasizes the importance of shared vision and collective responsibility in fostering peace and security. Feminist Institutionalism (18) also provides insights into how gender-sensitive policies can be institutionalized to ensure sustainable governance structures. The framework reflects this through the strong connections between F2 and other factors,

highlighting the role of shared authority in harmonizing diverse voices while addressing security challenges.

Vigilance, Aid & Empowerment (F3) reflects the practical application of Empowerment Theory (44), which focuses on enabling individuals and communities to take control of their circumstances and achieve desired outcomes. This factor also draws from Systems Theory (42), as it emphasizes the interconnectedness of vigilance and aid systems within a broader socio-political framework. In the context of EO 70, this factor ensures continuous support and empowerment for vulnerable groups, fostering resilience and long-term peacebuilding.

Integrated Response & Action (F4) represents the culmination of collaborative efforts and aligns with Systems Theory's emphasis on holistic approaches. This factor highlights the need for integrated, multi-stakeholder responses to complex issues, ensuring sustainability and adaptability. Feminist Institutionalism supports this by advocating for institutional frameworks that promote gender equity and shared empowerment. This factor highlights the need for integrated, multi-stakeholder responses to complex issues, ensuring sustainability and adaptability.

For instance, F1's emphasis on inclusivity feeds into F2's harmonization of voices, which subsequently strengthens F3's empowerment initiatives and F4's integrated actions. Together, these factors align with the theoretical underpinnings to create a comprehensive approach to addressing gender sensitivity under EO 70. This framework contextualizes the nuanced interactions between equity, authority, empowerment, and action, demonstrating their relevance in fostering sustainable peace and security in the Davao Region.

Figure 1: Presented The Gender Sensitivity Framework.

The Gender Sensitivity Index of E.O. 70: NTF-ELCAC in Davao Region the Relative Importance Index (RII) of the Gender Sensitivity Index (GSI) for EO 70 in the Davao Region provides critical insights into stakeholders' perceptions and priorities regarding gender sensitivity. The highest-ranked factor, Shared Authority & Harmonized Security (RII = 0.854), underscores the paramount importance of inclusive decision-making processes and equitable representation in peace and security initiatives. This aligns with EO 70's focus on inclusive governance as a strategy for addressing local conflicts and fostering community-driven solutions. The prominence of this factor reflects stakeholders' recognition of the need for collaborative approaches where diverse voices, particularly those of women, are integrated into the framework of security and governance.

The second-ranked factor, Integrated Response & Action (RII = 0.848) highlights the value of cohesive and coordinated efforts in addressing gender sensitivity. This suggests that stakeholders prioritize unified and systematic approaches that enhance the implementation of EO 70. The high RII of this factor points to a strong preference for multi-stakeholder collaboration that not only ensures inclusivity but also drives sustainable outcomes in peacebuilding efforts. It reflects the importance of synergy between local government units, civil society, and community leaders in achieving gender-responsive development. Ranking third, Vigilance, Aid & Empowerment (RII = 0.845) emphasizes the critical role of continuous support and empowerment in addressing gender-related issues. While slightly lower than the top two factors, this RII indicates that

stakeholders view vigilance and empowerment as foundational for fostering resilience and equity among marginalized groups, particularly women. This factor aligns with the broader objectives of EO 70, which seeks to build community capacities and address vulnerabilities through targeted interventions and sustained empowerment initiatives.

Finally, Collaborative Equity & Inclusivity (RII = 0.754) ranks lowest among the four factors but remains an essential aspect of gender sensitivity in the EO 70 context. Its relatively lower RII suggests that while equity and inclusivity are recognized as critical, stakeholders perceive other factors such as security, empowerment, and integrated actions as more immediately impactful. This may point to a gap in the practical integration of inclusivity measures or a need for further advocacy and institutional support to elevate its importance in the broader implementation framework.

In summary, the RII rankings highlight nuanced priorities within the context of EO 70 in the Davao Region. Stakeholders place the highest importance on shared authority and harmonized security, followed closely by integrated response and empowerment. The findings suggest a strategic focus on participatory governance, systemic collaboration, and empowerment while acknowledging the need to further emphasize inclusivity and equity. These insights provide a roadmap for policymakers and practitioners to refine their approaches to gender sensitivity in peacebuilding and development efforts in the region.

Table 7: Presented The Relative Importance Index of the Study.

Factor	Relative Importance Index (RII)	Rank
Collaborative Equity and Inclusivity	0.754	4
Shared Authority and Harmonized Security	0.854	1
Vigilance, Aid, and Empowerment	0.854	3
Integrated Response and Action	0.848	2

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the null hypothesis stating that “the dimensions to the Gender Sensitivity Framework of Executive Order No. 70 in Davao Region is not factorable” is rejected. The study identifies a four-factor model Collaborative Equity and Inclusivity, Shared Authority and Harmonized Security, Vigilance, Aid and Empowerment, and Integrated Response and Action as key dimensions of gender sensitivity under EO 70. This evidence-based framework validates the existence of specific dimensions that contribute to addressing gender equity and inclusivity in local peace and security initiatives. The study’s four-factor model provides a comprehensive, evidence-based framework for addressing gender sensitivity in the context of E.O. 70. The current framework of gender sensitivity in the Davao Region under E.O. 70 highlights existing practices that integrate gender equity and inclusivity into local peace and security initiatives. However, the principles of inclusivity and responsiveness outlined in E.O. 70 can be interpreted to encompass gender sensitivity as a critical component of sustainable peace efforts.

In practice, integrating gender perspectives into

the implementation of E.O. 70 would involve ensuring that peace-building initiatives address the unique experiences and needs of all genders, promoting equal participation, and safeguarding the rights of women and gender-diverse individuals within the framework of ending local communist armed conflict. Incremental improvements are feasible through targeted interventions, such as enhancing feedback mechanisms, refining training materials, and addressing barriers to the participation of gender-diverse individuals in peace and security initiatives. Strengthening community engagement and providing additional support for GBV survivors could further improve the program’s effectiveness.

The study concludes that while the current gender sensitivity framework under EO 70 incorporates various practices aimed at promoting inclusivity and equity, certain redundancies and gaps in the indicators were identified. This indicates a need for refinement to optimize the framework’s effectiveness. Incremental improvements, such as strengthening community engagement, refining training tools, and addressing barriers to participation, are necessary to ensure a more inclusive and equitable approach.

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